

DIGITAL LITERACY EVALUATION

OVERVIEW

This document presents the preliminary evaluation results of the Digital Literacy Programme (DLP) run by Code Your Future. The evaluation is part of the REMEDIS project, aimed at co-developing improvements and measuring impact of Media Literacy and Digital Skills interventions in Europe. Twelve organisations in six countries partnered with the REMEDIS academic team to evaluate and explore improvement opportunities for interventions aimed at vulnerable groups.

OBJECTIVE

This is a summary of the evaluation applied in two cohorts in London (March and April, 2024), with a characterisation of the trainees and the differences observed between the pre-test and an immediate post-test on Digital Literacy, Internet Use and Expected Outcomes

SOCIO - DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

The majority of the trainees have a low socio-economic status, with a high proportion having refugee or asylum seeker status. 31 of them took the pre-test and 18 took the post-test

Gender (%)

58.1

38.7

3.2

Mean Age

45

Occupation (%)

Access

55% of the
participants
had only a
smartphone to
access Internet

DIGITAL SKILLS (%)

Improvements in all domains were observed, especially in **Technical** and **Information** skills

Content creation skills reported comparatively more modest gains

INTERNET USE (%)

Overall, participants increased their intentions to do different activities on Internet by 29%.

Finance-related activities, such as online shopping and mobile banking, presented an important increase after the course.

OUTCOMES

Participants were optimistic about the expected positive outcomes after the course, especially for **Education** and **Informal Learning**.

Social relations (formal and informal) improvements were relatively lower.

Thank
you

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The DLP and its evaluation would not be possible without the work done by all the volunteers, charities and other civic organisations that joined efforts to support the course and drive positive impact through Media and Digital Literacy interventions.